

Development of Ultra-High Performance Concrete with Local Materials in Cambodia

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents an approach to design concrete mixtures. It is based upon a set of models relating local composition and engineering properties of concrete, to be implemented Ultra-High Strength Concrete using in Cambodia. A global approach to concrete is promoted, where performance specifications can be formulated in terms of composition concrete (water-cement ratio, cement, aggregate, sand, and admixture).

Keywords: Ultra high Performance Concrete, Strength

1. INTRODUCTION

Here introduce the paper, and put a nomenclature if necessary, in a box with the same font size as the rest of the paper. The paragraphs continue from here and are only separated by headings, subheadings, images and formulae. The section headings are arranged by numbers, bold and 9.5 pt. Here follows further instructions for authors.

Ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC) is a novel construction material exhibiting enhanced mechanical and durability properties, which can lead to economical construction through reducing the cross-sections of structural members with associated materials savings and lower installation and labor costs [1]. The relatively high initial cost of UHPC has restricted its wider use in the construction industry. However, ongoing research and investigations are filling knowledge gaps in order to commence innovative UHPC having reduced initial cost.

In this highly packed particles skeleton, the aggregate plays an important role in normal concrete and UHPC, the aggregate could directly affect mechanical and durability properties in normal concrete [2-5], similarly, the aggregate also affect these properties of UHPC [6,7]. Nowadays, based on available literature, the most widely used fine aggregates in UHPC was natural river sand. However, one alarming fact, which should never be ignored, that the natural river sand is non-renewable resource. In some regions, RS has already been exceedingly exploited, which has threatened the safety of bridges, the stability of river banks, and ecological system [8-9]. Besides, the natural river sand is a typical local material.

In this study, the properties of local constituents for mixing design of UHPC was tested. Compression and flexural Strength was obtained ACI & ASTM. This research contribute with to this study of concrete in Cambodia.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Overview

In order to establish a procedure for mix design, a linear projection of compressive strength versus w/c ratio from Design of Normal Concrete Mixes method was considered initially beyond the limiting w/c ratio of 0.3[9]. A broad combination of ACI and BS methods was used to proportion cement/binder, coarse aggregate, sand and superplasticizer. An initial estimate of density was made and later adjusted in the light of values actually obtained. High strength high performance concrete mix for characteristic strengths of 100MPa was designed using ordinary Portland cement (ASTM C150) [10] with 10% sand conforming to ASTM C778 [11], sand size for (20-30) model. A UHPC-S1 for 100 MPa, without aggregate was also designed for comparison purposes.

Table-1: Constituents of UHPC

Strength	W/C Ratio	Cement (kg)	Silica Fume (kg)	Sand (kg)	Aggregate (kg)	Water (L)	Superplasticizer (%)
UHPC	0.168	475	74	593	1068	110	3.77
UHPC-S1	0.168	475	74	682	1068	110	2.40

2.2 Materials

2.2.1 Cement

ASTM Type I Portland cement were used in the concrete mixtures. The chemical and physical properties of cement ash are given in Tables-2, respectively.

Table-2: Chemical compositions of cement

Properties	Density (g/cm^3)	Specific Surface Area (cm^2/g)
Cement	3.071	3526

2.2.2 Fine Aggregate

Natural sand as per ASTM C-33-2018 [12] was used. Locally available River sand having bulk density 2,606 kg/m³ was used. The properties of fine aggregate are shown in Table-3.

Table-3: Sieve Analysis of Fine Aggregate

Sieve Size (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	Cum.Weight Retained (g)	Cum.Retained (%)	Actual Test (%)
9.5	130	130	3.64	96.36
4.75	1852	1982	55.55	44.45
2.36	805	2787	78.11	21.89
1.18	259	3046	85.37	14.63
0.600	141	3187	89.32	10.68
0.300	95	3282	91.98	8.02
0.150	80	3362	94.23	5.77
0.075	45	3407	95.49	4.51

Natural sand is testing in ASTM D2419-2022 [12] for sand equivalent test, the result testing are shown in Table-4.

Table-4: Sand Equivalent test of Fine Aggregate

Sample No	H1	H2		Sand Equivalent (%)	
	Floculat	Visual	Piston	Visual	Piston
1	11.7	10.1	9.6	86.32	82.05
2	11.8	10.1	9.7	85.59	82.20
3	11.9	10.1	9.8	84.87	82.35
Average=				85.60	82.20

2.2.3 Coarse Aggregate

Natural and recycled aggregates were used as the coarse aggregate in the concrete mixtures. Crushed natural granite was used as the natural aggregate. The recycled aggregates were obtained by crushing old concrete cubes previously prepared in the laboratory. The strength grades of the cubes (28-day

designed compressive strength) ranged from 30 to 100 MPa. Natural coarse aggregate with bulk density 2.656 kg/m³ was used in the concrete mixtures. The physical properties of the aggregate are given in Table-5.

Table-5: Sieve Analysis of Coarse Aggregate

Sieve Size (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	Cum.Retained (%)	Actual Test (%)
19.00	0	0	100
12.50	0	0	100
9.50	101	2.27	97.73
4.75	3851	86.66	13.34
2.36	4431	99.71	0.29

Coarse Aggregate is testing for Los Angeles, the result is shown in Table-6.

Table-6: Los Angeles Test of Coarse Aggregate

No	Description	Result Test
A	Grading	C
B	Spheres	8
C	500 Revolutions	500
D	Initial Weight	5000
E	Final Weight on Sieve 1.68mm	4470
F	Loss (D-E)	530
G	Percent of Wear (F/D)x100	10.6

Coarse Aggregate is testing for Elongation Index, the result is shown in Table-7.

Table-7: Elongation Test of Coarse Aggregate

Sieve Size Square (mm)	Gauge Length (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	Weight Passing (g)	Total Weight (g)	Result Test (%)
63.5-50.8	102.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	
50.8-37.5	80.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
37.5-28.0	57.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	
28.0-20.0	39.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	
20.0-14.0	28.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	
14.0-10.0	20.1	7.9	360.3	368.2	
10.0-6.3	14.2	58.3	179.3	237.6	
Total		66.2	539.6	605.8	10.93

Coarse Aggregate is testing for Flakiness Index , the result is shown in Table-8.

Table-8: Flakiness Test of Coarse Aggregate

Sieve Size Square (mm)	Gauge Length (mm)	Weight Retained (g)	Weight Passing (g)	Total Weight (g)	Result Test (%)
63.5-50.8	33.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	
50.8-37.5	26.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	
37.5-28.0	19.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	

28.0-20.0	14.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	
20.0-14.0	10.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	
14.0-10.0	7.2	284.8	83.4	368.2	
10.0-6.3	4.9	187.8	49.8	237.6	
Total		472.6	133.2	605.8	21.99

2.2.4 Superplasticizer

In this study, a superplasticizer Sikaplast8588 ACE [13] was used in all the concrete mixtures. Sikaplast8588 ACE contains no added chloride and weighs approximately 2.4% per cement 100kgs.

Fig-1: Superplasticizer

2.3 Mixing Procedures

Fine and coarse aggregates were added together in the mixer. Then one-third of the water was added followed by the air-entraining agent. Cement is then added (after 30s) along with the rest of water and followed by the pozzolanic materials. The concrete was mixed in the mixer with all the ingredients for about three to four minutes. Then the superplasticizer was added and the mix was allowed to mix for three more minutes. The batch was then placed in plastic cube 100 mm in two layers while vibrating the specimens.

2.4 Specimens and Curing

Following test samples were prepared for testing the 100MPa concrete and the control specimen for laboratory testing.

1. 100mm cubes for compressive strength testing.
2. 100x100x400mm beams for flexural strength testing.
3. 100mm cubes for measuring density of concrete.
4. All specimen were cured in water at 20°C for 28 days before testing.

The cube sample size is 100x100x100mm and flexural beam mold 100x100x400 mm for series I and II were demolded after 24 h and the specimens were wet cured in the curing room until time of testing. For each mix, approximately 27 cubes were prepared and tested for strength and flexural testing. Slump tests and flow slump test were conducted on fresh concrete following ASTM C143 [14] and C1611 [15], respectively.

2.5 Testing procedures

The compressive strength tests are done in accordance with ASTM C-39 [16]. Three 100 mm cubes were tested for strength at 7 and 28 days, three cubes were tested for the modulus of elasticity at 7 and 28 days and three beam were tested for strength at 7 and 28 days. Tests for strength and flexural testing were carried out on the same day using a 2,000 kN Digital hydraulic testing machine equipped with a swivel-head platen. All specimens tested for modulus were subjected to identical initial loadings regardless of the compressive strength. This initial cycle of loading and unloading was repeated at least twice before the specimen was loaded to the desired load level. The tests on modulus of elasticity were loaded to a maximum stress equal to 40% of the maximum compressive strength according to ASTM C469 [17]. The loading rate was constant at 0.2–0.24 MPa/s. The load and the deformation were recorded for each specimen and the value of the elastic modulus was calculated from recorded loads and deformations according to ASTM. Test specimens and various curing methods are shown in Fig. 2. For all series, strength and modulus tests were conducted at 7, and 28 days. Stress-Strain curves have calculation by equation as showing:

$$\frac{f_c}{f_c^*} = \frac{n \left(\frac{\epsilon_c}{\epsilon_o}\right)}{n - 1 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_c}{\epsilon_o}\right)^{nk}}$$

Where f_c^* Stress obtained from compression test

ϵ_o Strain when f_c reach f_c^*

n a curve-fitting factor equal to $\frac{E_c}{E_c - E_c^*}$ or $n = 0.8 + \left(\frac{f_c}{2500}\right)$

E_c initial tangent modulus (where $\epsilon_c = 0$)

$E_c^* = f_c^*/\epsilon_o$

k a factor to control the slopes of the ascending and descending branches of the stress–strain curve, taken equal to 1.0 for ϵ_c/ϵ_o less than 1.0 and taken greater than 1.0 for ϵ_c/ϵ_o greater than 1.0.

Fig-2: UHPC-S1 Mixing

Fig-3: Stress-Stain for UHPC (9 Samples)

3. RESULT AND DICUSSION

Table-9. High Performance Concrete Testing Result

Author	Mix	W/C Ratio	Cube Strength 7days (MPa)	Cube Strength 28days (MPa)	Flexural Strength 7days (MPa)	Flexural Strength 28days (MPa)
Ahmed Al Mohammedi	UHPC	0.168	85.00	100	10.63	12.50
Present Work	UHPC-S1	0.168	91.35	107.4	10.89	12.82
		0.168	93.18	109.6	11.04	13.45

	0.168	92.73	109.1	11.97	13.05
	0.168	92.48	108.8	10.74	12.56
	0.168	92.06	108.3	11.01	12.59
	0.168	91.42	105.2	10.8	12.79
	0.168	94.05	110.7	11.45	13.27
	0.168	94.94	111.5	10.75	12.55
	0.168	94.78	110.2	11.01	13.65

3.1 Compressive strength

Compressive strength tests on UHPC-S1 concrete specimen at 7 and 28 days shows in figure 3 that the rate of development of strength of concrete containing 15% Portland cement replaced with sand was similar to that for UHPC specimen though slightly slower than the UHPC concrete mix. The compressive strengths of UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% Portland cement replaced with aggregate was somewhat higher than the UHPC specimen. The compressive strength of specimen kept increasing up to 28 days when the specimen could achieve design strengths. This is typical of concretes with low w/c ratios in which hydration of cement is slow and needs water from external sources for hydration [4-6]. UHPC-S1 concrete developed about 85.33% of its design strength in 7 days while complete design strength of UHPC-S1 developed in 28 days.

During the testing of specimen, it revealed that complete section of UHPC-S1 concrete specimen failed suddenly on reaching failure loads while the paste and the sand failed simultaneously at the failure interface. This kind of failure is typical of high strength concretes [4,5]. Sudden failure of specimen can cause damage/ injury and necessary protective measures are required to be taken.

Fig-4: UHPC-S1 Compression Testing

3.2 Flexural strength

The flexural strength of UHPC-S1 concrete show in figure 4 containing 15% replacement of sand have been observed to possess 0.4 to 9.2% higher flexural strength as compared to UHPC specimen. Higher flexural strengths are certainly a consequence of higher compressive strengths and increased density of concrete containing sand due to which a finer microstructure results on formation of hydration products of binder in concrete to the point of failure, typical of high strength concretes. Testing of concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand resulted into higher static and dynamic moduli as compared to similar concrete with Portland cement only.

Fig-5: UHPC-S1 Flexural Testing

3.3 Static modulus of elasticity

The average static modulus of elasticity for UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand has been observed to be 4.46% higher than the UHPC specimen. Static modulus of elasticity for UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of cement is observed to be around $49,100\text{N/mm}^2$ compared to $47,000\text{N/mm}^2$ for concrete containing Portland cement only.

$$E_c = 4700\sqrt{f'_c}$$

3.4 Density of hardened concrete

The average saturated and oven-dried densities for UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement was observed to be 2501 and 2556g/m^3 respectively, as compared to UHPC mixes which were 2440 and 2539kg/m^3 , respectively. The saturated and dry densities of UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand are about 2.5% higher than the UHPC mixes. Better hydration and packing of finer materials in UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand results into lower absorption and higher density as compared to UHPC mixes.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Satisfactory UHPC-S1 mixes with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand can be designed. UHPC-S1 concrete specimen with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand developed about 8.98% higher compressive strengths, 3.76% higher flexural strength, 4.46% higher static moduli of elasticity, 2.5% higher density, resistance as compared to control specimen. UHPC-S1 concrete with 15% replacement of Portland cement with sand certainly improves the strength and durability of such Ultra high-performance concrete making it a more acceptable material for major construction projects.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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